

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Development of a new model of insulin sensitivity in patients with type 2 diabetes and association with mortality

Stefano Ciardullo^{1,2*}, Alessandro Roberto Dodesini^{3*}, Giuseppe Lepore³, Anna Corsi³,
Cristiana Scaranna³, Gianluca Perseghin^{1,2}, Roberto Trevisan^{2,3}

¹ Department of Medicine and Rehabilitation, Policlinico di Monza, Monza, Italy

² Department of Medicine and Surgery, University of Milano Bicocca, Milan, Italy

³ Endocrine and Diabetology Unit, Azienda Socio Sanitaria Territoriale Papa Giovanni XXIII, Bergamo, Italy

* These authors contributed equally to this work and served as co-first authors.

Supplementary Table 1 Results of the Cox proportional hazard model evaluating the association between all included variables and all-cause and cardiovascular mortality in the NHANES population.

	All-cause mortality			Cardiovascular mortality		
	HR	95%CI	p	HR	95%CI	p
Age (years)	1.07	1.06 - 1.09	<0.001	1.08	1.05 - 1.11	<0.001
Female sex	0.69	0.58 - 0.83	<0.001	0.46	0.34 - 0.63	<0.001
Race-Ethnicity						
Non-Hispanic white	1.0			1.0		
Hispanic	0.96	0.78 - 1.18	0.679	1.14	0.68 - 1.91	0.607
Non-Hispanic Black	1.02	0.85 - 1.23	0.844	1.00	0.67 - 1.50	0.986
Other	1.08	0.68 - 1.71	0.734	1.13	0.42 - 3.01	0.809
Education	0.81	0.73 - 0.90	<0.001	0.87	0.70 - 1.07	0.186
Cigarette smoke						
Never	1.0			1.0		
Past	1.13	0.91 - 1.39	0.262	1.01	0.71 - 1.43	0.951
Current	1.92	1.53 - 2.43	<0.001	1.94	1.17 - 3.21	0.011
CKD	1.49	1.21 - 1.83	<0.001	1.35	0.81 - 2.24	0.248
Heavy alcohol consumption	1.10	0.66 - 1.82	0.721	0.99	0.33 - 2.99	0.981
Cholesterol, total (mg/dL)	1.00	1.00 - 1.00	0.978	1.00	1.00 - 1.00	0.682
Blood pressure	0.99	0.92 - 1.07	0.841	1.17	0.96 - 1.44	0.121
CVD	1.53	1.29 - 1.82	<0.001	2.28	1.54 - 3.36	<0.001
Estimated GDR						
Q1	1.0			1.0		
Q2	0.54	0.43 - 0.69	<0.001	0.47	0.29 - 0.76	0.003
Q3	0.61	0.50 - 0.75	<0.001	0.58	0.35 - 0.95	0.031
Q4	0.42	0.32 - 0.55	<0.001	0.45	0.25 - 0.81	0.008

Abbreviations: GDR, glucose disposal rate ($\text{mg kg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$).